

Assessment on HIV Testing Among Newly Diagnosed Tuberculosis Patients at the National Hospital for Respiratory Diseases (NHRD) in Welisara, Sri Lanka during the first quarter of 2024

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ABSTRACT: This study was aimed to assess and review the current practice of screening of HIV in TB patients within NHRD Welisara hospital against the recommended standard practice by the National Guideline and the cross-sectional study was conducted on newly diagnosed tuberculosis patients. Simple random sampling was used to collect data from a sample size of 163, with retrospective data gathered from patient ward records. Data quality was enhanced by reviewing clinic and laboratory records, and a secure Excel spreadsheet was maintained for data management.

Results: Data indicated that 12.3% (n=20) lacked documentation for HIV testing. Of the 143 patients tested, only 43.4% (n=62) were tested while in the ward; others were tested at follow-up clinics. The average time from TB confirmation to HIV testing was 4.8 days (range: 0 to 36 days). Though average post-TB diagnosis hospital stay was 20.9 days (range: 0 to 129 days) for HIV tested patients, those without HIV testing had an average stay of 12 days (range: 0 to 40 days).

The primary reason for not undergoing HIV testing was patient transfer, but with an average ward stay of 14.6 days post-TB diagnosis. Other factors included patient death, disappearance, or leaving against medical advice. Notably, four patients were discharged without HIV testing, having stayed 3 to 11 days post-TB diagnosis. Most patients (51.7%, n=74) were tested at the NHRD laboratory, while 39.9% (n=57) were tested at an STD clinic, and only 5.6% underwent RDTs in the ward.

Conclusion: Those without HIV testing had prolonged hospital stays, suggesting missed opportunities. Underutilization of RDTs by ward staff needs attention. Incorporating HIV test results into the discharge checklist may prevent these oversights. Therefore, findings will be presented to the director-NHRD aiming to initiate a discussion and create an audit cycle.

KEY WORDS: HIV test, Newly diagnosed tuberculosis, Welisara Sri Lanka.

INTRODUCTION

All tuberculosis patients should be screened for HIV at diagnosis or during follow-up if not initially tested as a provider-initiated testing. Rapid HIV diagnostic tests (RDT) have recently been introduced at selected TB units to facilitate delays. Tuberculosis (TB) and HIV coinfection (HIV/TB coinfection) represents a severe and life-threatening combination throughout the world [3–4]. Despite continuous efforts by the World Health Organization (WHO), TB remains the main cause of death for people living with HIV/AIDS [10, 11]. In 2022, the global percentage of notified TB cases with a documented HIV test result was 80%. While a high testing coverage of 94% is reported by the WHO for the European region, However, in 2016, the WHO estimated that only 57% of notified cases of TB were aware of their HIV status [15]. The WHO reported that of the 31,079 TB patients notified in 2016, 84% were screened for HIV. Of them, 6% were HIV positive [14]. the most recent data for the European Union published in 2018 show a test rate of 73.4% only, suggesting that the prevalence of HIV among TB patients may be underestimated [13]. Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection is a major global public health issue, with 650 000 deaths from HIV-related causes reported in 2021 [11]. According to the latest data released by the World Health Organization (WHO), tuberculosis (TB) accounts for approximately 30% of the 690 000 acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS)-related deaths worldwide [12]. To normalize the HIV diagnosis and minimize delays, pre-test information and testing was introduced with full range of services. Multimodal HIV testing services is being used to increase the testing accessibility, availability, acceptability and affordability to all the people and it

is no longer limited to high-risk groups. In par with these Sri Lanka developed of system to test HIV among tuberculosis patients and testing tuberculosis in HIV patients has been introduced.

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was conducted on newly diagnosed tuberculosis patients at NHRD Welisara Sri Lanka in the first quarter of 2024.

The NHRD is a leading tertiary care hospital in Sri Lanka specializing in respiratory diseases, with a capacity of 382 beds. A significant portion of its patients are tuberculosis (TB) cases, and the hospital has a dedicated ward for multi-drug-resistant TB.

[9]. Simple random sampling was used to collect data from a sample size of 163, with retrospective data gathered from patient ward records. Quality was enhanced by data triangulations using clinic and laboratory records, and a secure Excel spreadsheet was maintained for data management. The demographic data and other qualitative variables were presented as numbers and percentages.

RESULTS

The total number of TB diagnoses for the quarter 1 of year 2024 was and the calculated sample size was Data indicated that 12.3% (n=20) lacked documentation for HIV testing. Of the 143 patients tested, only 43.4% (n=62) were tested while in the ward; others were tested at follow-up clinics. The average time from TB confirmation to HIV testing was 4.8 days (range: 0 to 36 days). Though average post-TB diagnosis hospital stay was 20.9 days (range: 0 to 129 days) for HIV tested patients, those without HIV testing had an average stay of 12 days (range: 0 to 40 days).

The primary reason for not undergoing HIV testing was patient transfer, even though this category had an average ward stay of 14.6 days post-TB diagnosis. Other factors included patient death, disappearance, or leaving against medical advice. Notably, four patients were discharged without HIV testing, having stayed 3 to 11 days post-TB diagnosis. Most patients (51.7%, n=74) were tested at the NHRD laboratory, while 39.9% (n=57) were tested at an STD clinic, and only 5.6% underwent RDTs in the ward (Table 1).

Table 1. Number of HIV screening tests by Centers

Place where HIV test was carried out	Total (n=163)	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Chest hospital laboratory	74	45.40
STD Clinic	57	34.97
Inward testing	8	4.91
From a different government hospital lab	1	0.61
Private sector	3	1.84
Not tested	20	12.27
Total	163	

Table 2. Number of days between TB diagnosis and HIV testing

Number of days between TB diagnosis and HIV testing	Total (n=163)	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Same day	32	19.63
Between day 2 and one week	80	49.08
Between day 8 and one months (30 days)	28	17.18
More than 30 days	1	0.61
Already done before TB diagnosis	2	1.23
Not tested	20	12.27
Total	163	

Table 3. Identified possible reasons for not performing HIV testing

Identified reason for not doing HIV testing	Number of incidences	Number of days from TB diagnosis
Transfer to another hospital - Acute illness	9	0, 0, 0, 1, 10, 15, 24, 38, 39
Discharged	4	3, 3, 5, 11
Transfer to another hospital - non acute reasons	3	2, 7, 40,
Re-transfer to initial hospital*	1	14
Left against medical advice	1	27
Dead	1	1
Missing	1	0
Total	20	

*Patient was in a surgical ward during TB diagnosis

Table 4. Age Distribution of the patients who was tested for HIV vs not tested

Age in years	16-30	31-45	46-60	61-75	>76	Average
Age distribution of patients with both TB & HIV testing	16 (11.2%)	34 (23.8%)	49 (34.2%)	38 (26.6%)	6 (4.2%)	52.05 years
Age distribution of patients with only TB diagnosis	0	0	9 (45%)	4 (20%)	7 (35%)	67.55 years

All the HIV not tested patients belonged to male gender

DISCUSSION

Tuberculosis is one of the most frequent opportunistic infections which can be occur in people living with HIV, and on the other hand HIV greatly raises the chances of transitioning from latent TB infection to active TB. Therefore, the incorporation of HIV testing into TB programs has become fundamental in addressing these dual conditions.

Testing for HIV in TB patients helps to identify those with HIV-TB co-infection who need a different clinical approach, including timing of ART initiation and co-management of both diseases. Timely initiation of ART has dramatically reduced mortality in other co-infected patients[16]. Additionally, recognizing TB patients who are HIV-positive enables healthcare professionals to provide holistic counseling and support, helping to enhance adherence to treatments for both TB and HIV. Furthermore, diagnosing latent TB infection is also a part of this process where initiation of TB preventive therapy will drastically reduce active TB incidence among HIV patients.

NHRD Welisara is the major hospital treating tuberculosis patients, and it accepts transfers from all over the country. It is the hospital in Southeast Asia treating multidrug-resistant tuberculosis. Therefore, this setting was an ideal setting to asses HIV testing. In Europe, data on the HIV status of TB patients were available in about 70% of all cases [5,6]. Among the 21 European countries with documented HIV status, approximately 4% of all TB patients were HIV positive [6]. Germany is among the countries in which precise epidemiological data on HIV/TB coinfections are not available [18]. However, it is estimated that the proportion of active TB among HIV-positive patients is approximately 2.6% [5].

Despite the identified advantages, various barriers are preventing the establishment of routine HIV testing in TB patients. The stigma associated with HIV is one of the most common obstacles that makes patients reluctant to embrace testing. A study by Kigozi et al. (2021) in the sub-Saharan region of Africa, fear of discrimination was an important barrier to HIV testing in TB clinics[17]. Moreover, lack of access to HIV testing centers, especially in rural areas of Pakistan, increases the problem. Healthcare systems are constrained by human resources (in terms of adequately trained staff) and testing kits [18].

Up until the end of 2017, all inward and clinic samples had to be forwarded to the nearest STD clinic for HIV testing. Hospital staff frequently cited inadequate transportation options, lengthy turnaround times, and challenges in report collection as common

obstacles hindering sufficient HIV testing. In March 2018, in an effort to address these issues, the NSACP implemented rapid HIV testing facilities in base hospitals and higher-level institutions. This was a significant advancement in enhancing HIV testing within the hospital environment.

A study done at National Hospital Sri Lanka revealed that most healthcare workers were unwilling to take on additional tasks, viewing them as a burden because of their heavy workload, additionally, fewer HIV test requests were made by first contact doctors, who reported discomfort in offering HIV tests to patients and faced challenges in providing post-test counseling [20].

The rate of absent HIV testing in this audit is 12.3% and it is reasonably high level when as this is found in the national respiratory disease hospital. The average age of the group who had not received HIV testing is higher than that of the group which had undergone HIV testing (67.5 vs 52 years). No one aged less than 49 had missed the HIV testing. (table 4) Additionally the average time stay inside the ward since TB diagnosis for the patient group who failed to undergo HIV testing is 12 days. These observations may hint that there are true failures from the health care delivery point of view and can be due to service negligence by the healthcare worker (HCW) or possible stereotyping by the HCW that too old patients are too old to acquire HIV. Majority of patients who have not had HIV testing had ultimately been transferred to another hospital for other health issues, implying that HCW may have been too occupied with the patients' other medical condition and therefore forgotten the due HIV testing.

HIV testing is typically conducted within one week in most cases (approximately 69%) as shown in Table 2. This suggests that if HIV testing is not ordered promptly after a TB diagnosis, there is a significant risk of the test being missed. Globally, various strategies have been proposed and enacted to help to surmount these barriers with considerable variation in success. A key step is the integration of HIV testing into routine TB care as part of standard practice. Therefore, incorporating HIV testing into the checklist or bed head ticket alongside TB diagnosis could prove beneficial.

Very low use of HIV rapid testing at inpatient set up is a concern (table 1). Even in other parts of the world and even in Sri Lanka, availability point-of-care rapid diagnostic tests helped to increase testing uptake thanks to their simplicity in conduct and speed of receiving results[10]. Awareness and educational campaigns aimed at patients and healthcare workers can help reduce stigma and highlight the significance of HIV testing in the management of TB[19]. If the ward staff is more knowledgeable about the HIV and getting repeated training and awareness on HIV rapid test use at ward set up, the missing HIV test number could have been minimized. Task shifting, i.e. the process of teaching non-specialist healthcare workers how to do a test for HIV, is a proven method in the management and strengthening of access to and efficiency in the case of HIV/AIDS care in developing countries[18]. Besides that, the policy measures that not only make HIV testing free but might also partially for it can be good tool in motivating patients to take up the tests.

In efforts to scale up TB patients being tested for HIV, we have seen progress in these age old efforts around the world. For example, based on information from the World Health Organization, the WHO reports the testing of TB-infected patients with HIV has grown from 165 in 2004 to 88% in 2021 in endpoints of high burden countries, while the rest receive no funding performance on all targets, however, the joint implementation of these activities has been plagued by significant regional disparities, sub-Saharan Africa is regarded as the region which has taken up some initiatives and achieved the testing coverage due to the policies that are in place as well as the support from other countries, while regions like Southeast Asia and Eastern Europe countries to have difficulty in tracking TB infection because of their variation in the healthcare system[10].

The discharge summary sheet we have observed did not contain a check box for HIV testing and if this can be incorporated, we think that number of missing HIV testing could be minimized.

CONCLUSION

Though majority was ultimately tested for HIV, low contribution from inpatient testing raises concerns. Those without HIV testing had prolonged hospital stays, suggesting missed opportunities. Underutilization of RDTs by ward staff needs attention. Incorporating HIV test results into the discharge checklist may prevent these oversights. Further discussion with ward staff to identify the poor use of inpatient rapid testing is needed with more studies to gain a detailed picture and minimize missing opportunities.

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